

LAKBAY-DIWA ✨
Publishing

e-ISSN 3082-4397
p-ISSN 3082-5741

VOLUME 2 | ISSUE 1

ECHOES

of **EXPRESSION**

A Creative Folio

JANUARY 2026
MONTHLY ISSUE
NATIONAL

NATIONAL BOOK PUBLISHER IN THE PHILIPPINES
DTI Business Reg. No. 6488937
TIN 492-741-614
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Butuan City, Philippines
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DOI 10.5281/zenodo.18491660

The Role of Non-Institutional Correction in the Criminology Profession

The Professional Regulation Commission Board of Criminology has highlighted the basic competencies that Registered Criminologists must demonstrate in correctional administration. These competencies include, but are not limited to, the ability to understand, organize, and apply the processes of the Probation System from petition, investigation, grant, and denial or disqualification, to supervision, monitoring, violation of conditions, modification of conditions, suspension, revocation, trial, early discharge, and release of the probationer. This also encompasses a clear understanding of the roles of the probation officer, probation aides, and the victim or complainant in the probation process.

Similarly, Registered Criminologists are expected to understand, internalize, and apply the processes of the Parole System, including petition, review, and evaluation by the Bureau of Jail Management and Penology and Bureau of Corrections, investigation, grant by the Board of Pardons and Parole, denial or disqualification, supervision and monitoring, violations of conditions, changes in conditions, suspension, revocation, arrest of the parolee, early discharge, and eventual release. This competency also includes an appreciation of the roles of the parole officer and the victim or complainant in the parole process.

In addition, criminologists must understand, use, and evaluate various forms of clemency, such as Executive Clemency, including absolute and conditional pardons, commutations of sentence, and reprieves, as well as other relevant remedies granted by the courts. Other forms of clemency, such as the decriminalization of certain criminal acts, the repeal of penal or criminal laws, and amnesty, are likewise included. These competencies require familiarity with the processes and procedures governing grants, denials or disqualifications, supervision and monitoring, violations of conditions, changes in conditions, suspension, revocation, arrest of the grantee, early discharge, and release. Furthermore, Registered Criminologists must be able to apply relevant legal provisions on preventive imprisonment and allowances for good conduct, including the processes for granting time allowances, the requirements for granting such allowances, and the cancellation or revocation of such grants, as well as related provisions on the total or partial extinction of criminal liability.

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Volume II, Issue I (January 2026), National Circulation

ISSN (Online) 3082-4397 ISSN (Print) 3082-5741

Published Online at www.lakbaydiwapublishing.com

Publisher: Lakbay-Diwa Publishing

DTI Business Reg. No. 6488937 / TIN 492-741-614

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These competencies are needed in shaping future leaders in law enforcement and corrections, as clearly stipulated in Republic Act No. 11131, otherwise known as the Philippine Criminology Act of 2018. The law recognizes that among the many career opportunities available to Registered Criminologists are positions as jail or correctional officers, as well as parole and probation officers who practice correctional administration through a community-based approach to rehabilitation. Given this mandate, criminology schools in the Philippines closely monitor the course outcomes of Non-Institutional Correction to ensure that students are adequately prepared for these professional roles. This area of correction emphasizes rehabilitation as an alternative to imprisonment.

The offering of non-institutional corrections in the criminology curriculum enables students to develop a broader, more humane perspective on the rehabilitation of criminal offenders. Understanding the key functions of non-institutional correction in the administration of justice is imperative. Through this course, criminology students come to realize that imprisonment is not the sole means of holding offenders accountable. Non-institutional correction offers several significant advantages. First, the family members of the offender are spared further hardship, as family structures remain intact and offenders can continue providing support. Second, community-based rehabilitation is often more effective because offenders are not further exposed to hardened criminals, recidivists, and delinquents who may reinforce a cycle of criminal behavior. Third, the high cost of imprisonment is reduced, which is especially beneficial for a cash-strapped government. This reduction minimizes the need for an extensive bureaucracy, including personnel salaries, benefits, and privileges; capital outlays; operating expenses; facility maintenance; and inmate subsistence. Lastly, community-based rehabilitation programs allow for public participation and monitoring, which can contribute to a more meaningful and sustainable process of life renewal for offenders.

In conclusion, Non-Institutional Correction as a course serves as an eye-opener for criminology students, particularly regarding their future employment opportunities as parole and probation officers. It enables them to realize that there are more effective and humane alternatives to institutional confinement. Through a community-based approach to rehabilitation, non-institutional correction promotes therapeutic modalities and restorative justice, basically contributing to a more balanced and humane criminal justice system.